

Indoor Navigation of Robot Using Ultra-WideBand Indoor Positioning System (IPS)

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Abstract

Global Positioning System (GPS) will offer wonders within the localization of objects or individuals in exterior environment, one factor it cannot offer is acceptable trailing among an enclosed location. This constraint is solely a minor hassle for client merchandise conversely it will be a hefty concern for numerous industries which have faith in indoor pursuit. This is where DecaWave's line of Ultra-WideBand Real Time Location System (RTL) is initiated for trailing and locating tenacity. The DRTL comprises of a variety of DWM1001 devices which could be organized as associate degree anchor, a tag or a bridge node on a gateway. The tags are typically transportable, and anchors are mounted in situ. Gateway deployment is enforced for the DecaWave 1001 dev board. For the gateway arrangement the DWM1001 dev board is interfaced with the Raspberry pi model 3B. The interaction between the bridge node and Raspberry pi 3B archetypal is Bluetooth transmission and therefore the exchange of ideas between raspberry pi 3B paradigm and personal computer is local area network or Wi-Fi. While this information obtained from DecaWave 1001dev board can be monitored provided that users are connected over a parallel network, so as to observe and access the information from everywhere the web-application is evolved by pushing data to IBM cloud. The coordinate posture standards of anchors and tags information retrieved from the web-application will be monitored by the IBM cloud end users and it is prompt to make use of diligence. By exploitation of the web-application robot maneuvering in the enclosed space has been accomplished which provides the orientation, direction and movement of the automation in an interior vicinity.

Keywords: Global Positioning System (GPS), Real Time Location system (RTL), Ultra-WideBand (UWB), DecaWave Real Time Location System (DRTL).

1. Introduction

International Navigation Satellite System signals locomote line of sight which suggest that they withstand haze, goblet and synthetic however they won't transmit sturdy adequate signals to range inside, via the roofs and parapet of rock pile [1]. Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) will afford virtuous functioning and positioning in out of door systems, they are not scrupulous precise once it involves the enclosed locations or in GNSS-shorn of circumstances. Although variety of locality pursuit systems existing yet several of them are inept within the IoT field owing to position inexactitude and depleted information tariff. An Indoor Positioning System (IPS) is pre-owned to track down things or individuals in the interior regions by means of sensory information. IPS has turn out to be predestined in spaces resembling searching malls, hospitals, airports and other interior venues wherever routing and additional Location-Based Services (LBS) can ascertain to be requisite [2].

A Local Positioning System (LPS) is a technology accustomed to locate internal view, analogous to the GPS used to locate outside positions. This paper propounds the scrutiny of high- exactitude IPS supported UWB that could be a short-range (tactical) radio technology that can be used for indoor positioning. In distinction to Bluetooth Low Energy and Wi-Fi, positioning is completed with transit time methodology (Time of Flight, ToF) rather than the measurement of signal strengths [3]. In latest existence UWB has been burgeoning as a vigorous elucidation for high-precision internal positioning technology anticipated to its additional accurateness, huge bandwidth, enhanced dispersion and localization in GNSS starved of settings. UWB is sanctioning a wider assortment of collaborative and multi-robot relevance scenarios [4]. Multiple robots with UWB tags can be localized in real-time supported on entity ranging measurements to the rigid organization of anchors.

Robots turn out to be especially prevalent intended for household applications, hence the diminutive comings of contemporary internal steering technologies have to be conquered.

A robot localization approach for Indoor navigation based on UWB is presented that enables a robot to reckon its location surrounded by some space via reflexively receiving ultra-wideband radio signals from preset stance modules [5] [4]. Interaction from the predetermined position modules is one-way, allowing the system to scale to numerous robots, thus enables the robot to trail and achieve high-speed, vigorous motions.

2. Methodology

DecaWave is a company that uses UWB technology and TOA algorithms to ascertain the space amongst devices and fixed-location beacons to alleviate in distinct applications. The DecaWave DRTLS manager which is an android application for arrangement of DRTLS nodes supported on the unit that runs on Bluetooth. DWM1001 module operates further radical Two-Way-Ranging (TWR) Real Time Location System (DRTLS). UWB technique consisting of anchors and tags based on the DWM1001 module, gateway to link up the anchors and tags. This module is classically mounted on a PCB. The MDEK1001 equipment provides 12 DWM1001 modules mounted on “development” boards facultative system developers to appraise the merchandise. DecaWave’s DWM1000 module has been enforced and it created straight-forward for engineers to instigate internal RTLS into their systems with a 10cm degree of precision, low power expenditure, and extreme invulnerability to intrusion [6].

DecaWave has recently released their newest module which is the DWM 1001 provides more features than the DWM1000. A UWB RTLS uses a minimum of four anchors to locate a tag. To initialize the system at least one of the anchors must be configured as an “initiator”. The initiator anchor will start and control the network and allow other anchors to join and form a network. The results of UWB IPS are determined by the configuration of anchors and tags in such a way that the four anchors are placed at four corners of an indoor area in anti-clockwise direction and the tag acts as a user, the position and location of tag can be determined with respect to this four anchors. The functioning network operation is clearly shown in figure 1 and local configuration and visualisation of anchors and tags on the android application is depicted in figure 2.

Figure 1. Configuration of anchors and tags

Figure 2. Visualisation setup of MDEK 1001 on the android application

The operational parameters of MDEK1001 are customized and the parameters like sampling rate, time interval can be changed manually in DecaWave RTLS android application. The results were taken before and after changing the parameters manually. The basic positioning setup of MDEK1001 was done in a lab room of area 8x8m at G. Narayanamma Institute of Technology and Science for women, Hyderabad (GNITS), before changing parameters the error value obtained is 0.5m and after changing the parameters the error is minimized to 0.2m.

2.1 DWM1001 Update (Gateway deployment)

Further to improve the performance of UWB IPS, Gateway deployment has been implemented for the DecaWave DWM 1001 module. This gateway is used to push the data into the cloud which is used for the development of web application. The first step is to update each DWM1001-DEV with the latest version of PANS firmware for DWM1001. For the gateway setup required components are DWM1001-DEV board and a Raspberry Pi 3 model B (R3B). The DW1001-DEV board must be configured as a bridge node, which can be extracted from a MDEK1001 unit [7] [8]. Remove the DWM1001-Dev board from the plastic enclosure by unscrewing it. Soldering is required in order to connect the DWM1001-DEV pcb to the Raspberry R3B model, hence it is necessary to solder a 2x13 GPIO header long pins onto the pcb as depicted in figure 3. For the R3B (Raspberry pi 3 model B) model setup, the process is to flash the provided Raspberry Pi image to the micro-SD card [8]. In order to identify the IP address of the R3B, VNC viewer has to be downloaded and installed on PC. Gateway has been designed by attaching the bridge node (DWM1001-DEV board) with the Raspberry Pi R3B model as shown in figure 4.

Figure 3. DWM1001-DEV with additional long pin header

Figure 4. Raspberry Pi R3B model plus bridge node

The results of gateway deployment are obtained by setting up the Raspberry Pi 3B model as a gateway and then interfacing the DWM1001 module with Raspberry Pi 3B model. The position values of x,y,z coordinates obtained in DRTLS android application are compared with the values obtained from the VNC viewer. The position accuracy of anchors and tags data obtained from the gateway needs to be pushed into the cloud for the development of web-application. Since the data obtained from the gateway can only be

accessed to the users within the same network and it is limited to access to certain range, hence in order to access this data from anywhere in the world the cloud computation has to be performed by pushing the data to the cloud. In this scenario, for cloud computation IBM cloud is used.

2.2 Web-Application Development

For the web application development the code has been created in Node-RED flow editor of IBM cloud platform by connecting the required nodes for accessing the data from the cloud. After connecting all the nodes in Node-Red flow editor copy and paste the URL of Node-Red flow editor window on to a new chrome page then the positions of anchors and tags data which are placed in indoor region will be obtained on to the webpage as shown in figure 5. The white color dots indicates the tag position and on the top left the coordinate position values are displayed according to their movements.

Figure 5. Indoor view of tags and anchors data on the webpage

2.3 Robot Maneuvering

The robot used for indoor tracking operates using L293D IC which is a typical Motor Driver IC which allows the DC motor to drive instantaneously in any direction and DC motor used for all sort of robotics projects. The IC works on the principle of Half H-Bridge, this set up which is used to run motors both in clock wise and anti clockwise direction. The commands are given in the Node-red flow editor like forward, reverse, left and right directions. According to the command given the robot will be moving in required direction [10]. The Raspberry pi 3B model which is interfaced with the bridge node and along with that a tag to determine the location of robot these both equipments are attached to the robot through which navigation of robot is examined which is depicted in figure 6.

Figure 6. Connections of a Robot

3. Results

The proposed technique of UWB IPS for choosing the correct position estimation at inter-cell borders was tested experimentally in a warehouse by placing the anchors in anti-clockwise direction as shown in figure 7. For the localization test space, the robot was made to move along a certain path and the location of the robot was determined w.r.t to tag placed on robot. Very often, when the Robot is moving in a room, the transmission from the mobile tag would be received by anchors in the boundaries of other room as well. For example, when the Robot is at the end of room, as shown in fig. 7, the signals are only received by anchor 1, A2, A3 and A4. But as the Robot moves towards other room, other anchors, A5 and A6 would also start receiving the signals.

Figure 7. Robot maneuvering in a warehouse

4. Conclusions

From experimental results it is shown that the performance of UWB IPS is competent to conquer the issues at cell boundaries and choosing the preeminent estimation, therefore maintaining the high accuracy in the slightest degree points at intervals surrounded by the localization area. The results of the robot position estimations are obtained in a web application which is developed by using IBM cloud platform. Thus, the monitoring of robot in an indoor area is accessible to the users from anywhere. It can be seen that the UWB technique using gateway deployment has less than 20cm error at any point within the localization space. This indicates that the projected approach for choosing the indoor navigation of robot is functioning well.

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